

ROMANIAN JOURNAL

OF

VICTIMOLOGY

No.1/2025

BUCUREȘTI, 2025

EDITORIAL BOARD

Anželika BANEVIČIENĖ (Lecturer dr., Public Security Academy, Mykolas Romeris University, LITHUANIA)

Karin BRUCKMÜLLER (Prof. Dr., Faculty of Law, Sigmund Freud University, Vienna, AUSTRIA)

Dobrinka CHANKOVA (Prof. Dr., Faculty of Law, Varna Free University, BULGARIA)

Kim COVENT (Police Advisor at the local police department, in Ghent, BELGIUM)

Layla SKINNS (Prof. dr., Deputy Director of Research for KE&I/Director of the Centre for Criminological Research, School of Law, University of Sheffield, UK)

Gratiela SION (assoc. prof. "Spiru Haret" University/vice-president of the Romanian Society of Victimology, ROMANIA)

Rebecca STRINGER (assoc. prof. Rebecca Stringer, Sociology, Gender Studies and Criminology Programme, University of Otago, Dunedin, NEW ZEALAND)

Artinoupoulu VASILIKI (prof. dr. Panteion University of social and political sciences, Sociology department/Director of the Institute on Crime and Criminal Justice, European Public Law Organization, GREECE)

Gema Varona MARTÍNEZ (Director of the Basque Institute of Criminology, University of the Basque Country, SPAIN and President of the *World Society of Victimology*)

Carolina VILLACAMPA ESTIARTE (Prof. dr. Faculty of Law, Economics and Tourism, University of Lleida, SPAIN)

Jo-Anne WEMMERS (Full professor, School of Criminology and Researcher, International Center for Comparative Criminology (CICC), University of Montreal, CANADA)

The Editor-in-Chief

Aura Marcela PREDA (assoc. prof. "Spiru Haret" University and researcher Institute of Legal Research – Romanian Academy, president of the Romanian Society of Victimology, ROMANIA)

CONTENT

Introduction	5
Aura PREDA	
SECTION I – International conference - 27th May 2025	9
Benjamin Mendelsohn confronting the crime of crimes	9
Gema VARONA MARTÍNEZ	
Landmarks about Mendelsohn`s Case studies	20
Bogdan BUNECI	
Mendelsohn`s legacy in the Romanian Specialized Literature	27
Aura PREDA	
SECTION II - National conference with international participation - 29th November 2025	47
Snakes & Ladders: Measuring the Risks of Police-Corporate Security Non-Collaboration in Domestic-Workplace Violence	47
Varsha AVADHANY, Kim COVENT	
Discussion: The Istanbul Convention in Montenegro – Achievements and Future Steps	65
Mirko KOJOVIĆ	
Correlates of Sexual Assault Victimization in a Sample of American Indian Girls	73
Viviana ANDREESCU	
Gender Equality in Respecting Dignity	100
Mihaela AGHENIȚEI, Jafar SAMDANI	
Whistleblower protection: Between Integrity and Victimization	122
Crina - Bianca VEREȘ	

Introduction

The Romanian Journal of Victimology appeared as a natural consequence, as a qualitative leap necessary to complete and continue at another level the steps started in 2020 with the first national conference. Concretely, we are talking about the first edition of the national conference entitled "Landmarks on Victimology, victimization and victims in Romania", dedicated exclusively to this topic, due to a push coming from the staff of the Cost Action CA 18121: Cultures of Victimology: understanding processes of victimization across Europe. The scientific manifestation that took place on November 29 in 2020 was held in two sections: the first one involves psychologists, sociologists, medical doctors, and other professionals, while the second section was supported by jurists (lawyers, researchers, teachers).

The conference continued the following year, respectively 2021, also online due to the pandemic, under the auspices of the two initials partners institutions in the mentioned Cost action project, the Faculty of Legal and Administrative Sciences Bucharest of the "Spiru Haret" University, and the Faculty of Economic, Legal and Administrative Sciences, within the "George Bacovia" University, from Bacău, the event aroused the interest of a double number of participants compared to previous year, namely a total of 45 participants doubled from 2020, also divided into two sections. Another novelty that must be highlighted is that, even although initially the objective was to organize a national conference, our colleagues from the Republic of Moldova and an NGO from Italy responded to our call, so we added national conference with international participation. The latter one the attended NGO is in the Calabria area, and it has also as a goal the protection of victims of human trafficking, among whom there were also women from Romania. Considering the mentioned premises, since 2021 we completed the announced title of the conference, thus becoming Landmarks on Victimology, victimization and victims in/from Romania, but also the type of manifestation, namely a national conference with international participation.

One year later, on July 2022, we succeeded to create the Romanian Society of Victimology (<https://victimologie.ro>) and, since that year, the conference lasts 2 days, respectively Friday and Saturday, meaning we kept the two sections: in Romanian in the first day (Friday) and added the third one in English on Saturday. We tried to ensure a certain continuity of the partners with

whom we started these conferences, but at the same time we put effort to gathered other professionals, theoreticians and practitioners. The year 2023 registered new progress, both in the number of participants and in the diversity of professionals who got involved in this scientific event. However, if for the interventions in the Romanian language we ensure the publication in the volume of the conference for the articles sent by the participants, we found that it is necessary to take measures to publish also the intervention in English also because the value, novelty and usefulness of these should be known also to the general public. That is precisely why, after the fourth volume of the conference (in 2024), we focused our efforts on publishing some articles from the section in English. Thus, was born the first journal from Romania dedicated exclusively to victimological studies in our country and abroad. The journal is structured in several sections. So, the structure for this journal that we are proposing is: - Pages from the history of Victimology - Studies about victimization, victim's protection and rights - Chronicles, scientific manifestation, interviews (for the future) We tried to attract to the Editorial board renowned professionals from as many continents, faculties, universities etc. in the hope that the peer-review of the articles will ensure the qualitative level of the information. Also, we will focus to support the publication of the two issues of this journal annually, from Romanian Society of Victimology's (RSV) funds.

The first issue contains, mainly, the works from the section in English of the previous year's conference.

The second issue of the year 2024 collected articles from most of the participants enrolled in third section of our National Conference with international participation, from our traditional conference during November 2024.

The present volume, no.1/2025, consists of two main parts. The first part comprises some of the articles resulting from the presentations given on the occasion of an international conference dedicated for the commemoration of the founder of Victimology, Benjamin Mendelsohn, (according with Annex no.1) while the second part includes several articles from the traditional annual conference of the RSV, held over the course of two days (the first day in Romanian and the second in English- according with Annex no.2).

For the first event, at the initiative of the Romanian Society of Victimology (*RSV*), which was joined by the Israeli Society of Victimology (*ISV*) and the World Society of Victimology (*WSV*), we organized an event in memory

of the Romanian criminal lawyer of Jewish descent, Benjamin Mendelsohn. Also, the Italian Society of Victimology has a representative as a speaker, and then the representatives from the Serbian Society of Victimology come as an audience. The central theme of the event revolves around honoring Benjamin Mendelsohn, recognized as the "founder of victimology," to commemorate 125 years since his birth. Scheduled for May 27th, 2025, the conference highlights its connections to both Bucharest (Romania), and Jerusalem (Israel), it was to be conducted entirely in a virtual format and participation in this online event has been completely free of charge.

From the second event, we selected few oral presentations which became articles, reflecting information, concerns and themes perfectly tailored to communicate the essential details to professionals and academics interested in the field of victimology.

For the next issues we will process works sent to the email address: svr@victimologie.ro. If you think that you can send original, interesting things, useful reflections, legislative or institutional, administrative proposals to a wide audience that can contribute to improvement of this mentioned topic, we are waiting for your contributions to the email address. You will find the writing instructions for the articles on the website www.victimologie.ro or you will receive them by email. The journal will be published also on paper in a limited number, but it will be available on the RSV's site, open access journal.

We think that it is also mandatory/necessary to add the following:

- Each invitation contains some directions on the most important topic in this area to obtain interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary approaches mandatory for the needs of different types of victims / victimizations.

- Each author has full responsibility for all content provided for publishing.

The Editor-in-Chief
Aura Marcela PREDA

**SECTION I - International conference, Bucharest,
online - 27th May 2025**

Benjamin Mendelsohn Confronting the Crime of Crimes

Gema VARONA MARTÍNEZ¹

Abstract

The article is structured in six parts: an introduction, contextualization: on the paternity (and maternity) of Victimology, the neglect of macro-victimization or mass victimization, in particular international crimes in the first half of the 20th century, the so-called century of genocides, multilevel reasons explaining the oblivion, the evolution of an apparent contradiction, and some conclusions. Benjamin Mendelsohn and Hans von Hentig, considered the "fathers" of victimology, were themselves victims of Nazism but initially ignored state crimes and macro-victimisation, such as the Holocaust. Instead, early theories focused on interpersonal violence and victim-blaming, neglecting some unrecognised "mothers" of the field: abused women from the 1930s. By the mid-1960s, Mendelsohn's perspective shifted; he began condemning the dehumanization of totalitarian regimes and envisioned a broader victimology that included international crimes.

The article concludes that modern victimologists must continuously question their own biases, conduct research with victims, and uphold human rights to break the cycle of dehumanizing violence.

Key-words: paternity of Victimology, study of victims, criminal responsibility, revictimization processes

I. Introduction

¹ Director of the Basque Institute of Criminology/Kriminologiaren Euskal Institutua (IVAC/KREI) (University of the Basque Country) and President of the *World Society of Victimology*. This text is part of the research carried out by the consolidated research group GICCAS, as well as the project *Collective Identities and Criminal Justice: An Interdisciplinary Approach* (PID2022-138077OB-I00), funded by the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation within the 2022 call for Knowledge Generation Projects. A first version in Spanish can also be found in the book in honor of Prof. José Luis de la Cuesta, to be published in 2026.

Throughout my academic career, I have sought to bridge the gap between written law and law in action, understood as law experienced by victims, offenders, and law enforcement officials, among other stakeholders. To do so, we need to train ourselves to use socio-legal methodologies that are more empirical, in a qualitative and quantitative sense², going beyond the dogmatic view which, while necessary, is incomplete for understanding reality and proposing paths towards transformation. In my role as director of the Basque Institute of Criminology, founded by our admired Professor Antonio Beristain, a great pioneer of victimology in Spain who attended the first symposium in 1973, I hope to continue collaborating with victimology researchers, also in Romania, in this scientific passion for commitment to society and, specifically, to younger generations. This commitment encompasses a search not only for better criminal law but, as the German jurist and Minister of Justice during the Weimar Republic, Gustav Radbruch³, said and has been quoted so many times, something better than criminal law.

On this path of life, I believe that many of us have moved from criminal law and criminology to victimology, as an interdisciplinary social science concerned with the complex processes of victimisation and devictimisation and, in that sense, with a strong link to human rights and social justice on a global scale⁴. In relation to this concern, it is not a question of pitting the rights of one group against those of another (victims versus offenders), but rather of thinking about the common good, especially in these times of violent polarisation and the continuous symbolic use of criminal law.

To this end, I have chosen a topic that intersects with international criminal law, victimology and, as a cross-cutting issue, the principle of humanity in criminal law⁵. Specifically, these pages constitute an analytical study based on

² DE SOUZA, S. P./HAHN, L.: *The Socio-Legal Lab: An Experiential Approach to Research on Law in Action*, Tilburg: Open Press Tilburg University, 2022.

³ RADBRUCH, G.: *Vorschule der Rechtsphilosophie*, 1948 (Spanish translation, *Introducción a la Filosofía del Derecho*, Mexico: F.C.E., 1951).

⁴ VARONA, G.: *Approaching Victimology as Social Science for Human Rights: A Spanish Perspective*, Cizur Menor: Aranzadi, 2021.

⁵ See, among others, DE LA CUESTA, J. L.: "International Criminal Law and Human Rights," in BERISTAIN, A./DE LA CUESTA, J.L. (Compilers): *Protección de los Derechos Humanos en Derecho Penal Internacional y Español (Protection of Human Rights in International and Spanish Criminal Law)*, VII Summer Courses in San Sebastián, Donostia/San Sebastián: University of the Basque Country, UPV/EHU, 1989, pp. 11-20; DE LA CUESTA, J. L.: "From Criminal Policy to Victimology Policy (and Criminal Policy?)", in *Victimology Studies: Proceedings of the First Spanish Congress on Victimology*, Valencia: Tirant lo Blanch, 2005, pp.

a profound question that will be explored in an exploratory manner, leaving it open for further in-depth research. The aim is to reflect on the lost link in the legacy of lawyer and victimologist Benjamin Mendelsohn in relation to contemporary international crimes which directly affected him because of his Jewishness at the origins of victimology. To address this objective, I draw on the contribution that I was invited to present at the International Conference, entitled *Benjamin Mendelsohn - The Founder of Victimology*, organised by the Romanian Society of Victimology, the Israeli Society of Victimology, the Italian Society of Victimology and the World Society of Victimology on 27 May 2025 to celebrate the 125th anniversary of the birth of this 'father' of the discipline. Precisely, 2025 coincided with the 40th anniversary of the adoption by the United Nations General Assembly, in its resolution 40/34, of the Declaration on Basic Principles of Justice for Victims of Crime and Abuse of Power, as well as the reform of Directive 2012/29/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 establishing minimum standards on the rights, support and protection of victims of crime, and replacing Council Framework Decision 2001/220/JHA.

Archival documents have been used for this article, in addition to academic references typical of a review of the state of the art. I am indebted for the work carried out in recent years by the Victimology Group of the European Society of Criminology on the digital archive of Benjamin Mendelsohn⁶, which includes documents from the Hebrew University of Jerusalem and the University of Bucharest. The origin of this archive is largely due to Israeli professor Leslie Sebba⁷ and the impetus of Beatrice Coscas-Williams, also an Israeli professor at Western Galilee College, who is committed to peaceful understanding in the face of on-going political violence in this region of the world.

After providing a brief overview of Benjamin Mendelsohn's work, I will focus on the missing link or the question of why Mendelsohn, a victim of Nazism, as was, to a lesser extent, the other father of victimology, Hans von Hentig, did not reflect in their early writings on the macro-victimisation of the Holocaust or

197-244; and DE LA CUESTA, J. L.: "The relevance of the principle of humanity in criminal law and criminal policy", in *Criminal Law and Criminology*, no. 5, 2014, pp. 3-8.

⁶ See the website: https://huji.primo.exlibrisgroup.com/discovery/fulldisplay/alma9921246559403701/972HUJI_INST:972HUJI_V1.

⁷ See, among his works, SEBBA, L.: "The victim's role in the penal process: A theoretical orientation", in *The American Journal of Comparative Law*, 1982, pp. 217-240.

other mass victimisations that preceded or followed it⁸. Below, I will present some ideas that may help to understand this apparent contradiction and then observe Mendelsohn's own evolution, as reflected in his writings on genocide from the mid-1960s onwards. Finally, I will propose some lessons learned for ongoing victimological research, where there will always be obscure angles or hidden victimisation. These projections for the future are important because today this branch of knowledge is compulsory in some criminology degrees at law schools, as well as in justice studies and continuing education, as mandated by general and specific regulations relating to victims' rights, with respect to the different legal operators. In addition, there are postgraduate courses⁹ and specialised master's degrees at various universities, whose teaching staff regularly contribute, together with researchers from various institutions, to the many scientific journals in this evolving field of victimology.

II. Contextualisation: On the paternity (and maternity) of Victimology

As we shall see in the following paragraphs, it can be said that the motherhood of Victimology is an unrecognised but real motherhood: that of abused, murdered, raped or simply lesbian women who, in the 1930s, crossed the professional path of the so-called fathers of Victimology: the psychologist and German jurist Hans von Hentig (1887-1974)¹⁰, and the Romanian lawyer Benjamin Mendelsohn (1900-1998)¹¹. Together with other scientists of the time,

⁸ BERISTAIN, A.: "Today we are creating a new cosmopolitan and inclusive science: maximum victimology, after Auschwitz", in *Int'l Annals Criminology*, no. 43, 2005, pp. 95; BERISTAIN, A.: *The dignity of macro-victims transforms justice and coexistence: In tenebris, lux!* Madrid: Dykinson, 2010.

⁹ See, for example, the IVAC/KREI postgraduate course "Working with victims of traumatic experiences", which has been running for almost two decades without interruption, with more than thirty teachers from various disciplines and professions.

¹⁰ See VON HENTIG, H.: "Remarks on the interaction of perpetrator and victim", in *Journal of Criminal Law and Criminology*, vol. 31(3), 1940, pp. 303-309; and VON HENTIG, H. (1948). *The Criminal & His Victim; Studies in the Sociobiology of Crime*, New Haven: Yale University Press, 1948.

¹¹ See MENDELSON, B., "Méthode à Utilizer par le Défenseur Pour les Recherches Concertant la Personnalité du Criminel," in *Revue de Droit Penal et de Criminologie et Archives Internationale de Médecine Légale*, no. 8-9-10, 1937, pp. 877-891; MENDELSON, B.: "Le Viol en Criminologie et l'Importance de la Femme-Magistrat", in *La Giustizia Penale*, I-II-III-IV, 1940, pp. 28-50; Mendelsohn, B.: "The Victimology", in *Etudes Internationales de Psycho-Sociologie Criminelle*, no. 10, 1956, pp. 4-36; MENDELSON, B.: "The Origin of Victimology", in *Excerpta Criminologica*, no. 3, 1963, pp. 239-256; MENDELSON, B.: "Les infractions commises sous le régime nazi sont-elles des 'crimes' au sens du droit commun?", in *Revue du Droit International des Sciences*

these two men developed a series of theories, affecting particularly women, and carried out various empirical studies which, today, help us to understand our prejudices and to appreciate the progress that has been made since then in the field of victimology.

Both von Hentig and Mendelsohn were influenced by Freud's psychoanalysis¹² and its reflection in various literary works. Thus, the impact of the work of the Prague writer Franz Werfel (1890-1945) is often cited, with his short novel *The Guilty One Is Not the Murderer, but the Victim* (*Nicht der Mörder, der Ermordete ist schuldig*)¹³. In 1941, Hans von Hentig, a former soldier in the First World War who supported Palestinians, would be persecuted for his Bolshevik ideas and emigrate to the United States – where he was also unable to escape the suspicion of the authorities, later returning to Germany – published an article in which he pointed out the relationship between victims and offenders. In 1947, Benjamin Mendelsohn coined the term "victimology" internationally during a conference in Bucharest for the Romanian Psychiatric Association, the origin of which can be traced back to his seminal research published in 1937. In that period of time, in 1948, Hans von Hentig published *The Criminal and His Victim*, in which he offered a typology of victims based on physical, psychological and social characteristics that expanded Mendelsohn's six-type taxonomy. In any case, in relation to the English word, and in the absence of earlier sources, it seems that it was in 1949 that psychiatrist Frederic Wertham first used the word "victimology" in an American book entitled *The Show of Violence*¹⁴, which criticised the image of murderers as heroes, as reflected in American comics.

Mendelsohn was a Romanian lawyer and Zionist activist who was admitted to the Bucharest Bar Association in 1934. During his career as a lawyer, Mendelsohn became interested in the study of victims. Although he specialised in criminal defence, he began interviewing victims and witnesses. Mendelsohn realised that most victims had a pre-existing interpersonal relationship with their aggressor and, together with von Hentig and other later Anglo-Saxon authors,

Diplomatiques et Politiques, no. 4, 1965, pp. 3–11; and MENDELSON, B., "Victimology and Contemporary Society's Trends", in *Victimology*, no. 1, 1976, pp. 18–28.

¹² WESTWICK, A.: "Criminology and psychoanalysis", in *The Psychoanalytic Quarterly*, vol. 9(2), 1940, pp. 269–282. Cf. WINNIK, H. Z., "Two Unpublished Letters of S. Freud", in *The Israel Annals of Psychiatry and Related Disciplines*, no. 121, 1974, pp. 3–9.

¹³ WERFEL, F.: *Nicht der Mörder: der Ermordete ist schuldig; eine Novelle*. K. Wolff, 1922.

¹⁴ WERTHAM, F.: *The Show of Violence*, Doubleday, 1949.

gave rise to positivist or act-based victimology¹⁵, which focused on the contribution of victims to crime, what would later be known in some countries as victim dogmatics¹⁶.

III. The neglect of macro-victimisation or mass victimisation, in particular international crimes in the first half of the 20th century, the so-called century of genocides

Victimology as a discipline was born in the 1930s¹⁷, a period between two World Wars and other mass victimisations¹⁸, including the dehumanisation of colonialist expansions¹⁹. However, most of the initial reflection in victimology focused on interpersonal violence and a perspective of victim blaming. The question is why, if the fathers of victimology were personally affected by wars and Nazism, they did not carry out a victimological theorisation beyond interpersonal violence and, moreover, in a non-blaming way²⁰.

¹⁵ See HOFFMANN, H.: "What Did Mendelsohn Really Say?", in BEN DAVID, S./KIRCHHOFF, G. F. (Eds.): *Faces of Victimology*. Mönchengladbach, 1992; KIRCHHOFF, G. F.: "Laudatio for Benjamin Mendelsohn Given at the Closing Session. In International Debates of Victimology. Papers and Essays Given at the VIIth International Symposium on Victimology in Rio de Janeiro 1991", in *World Society of Victimology Newsletter*, no. 11/12, 1993/1994, pp. 70-72; WEMMERS, J.-A., *L'histoire de la victimologie*. In *Introduction à la victimologie*, Montreal: Presses de l'Université de Montréal, 2003; WEMMERS, J.-A.: "A Short History of Victimology", in HAGEMANN, O./SCHÄFER, P./SCHMIDT, S. (Eds.). *Victimology, Victim Assistance and Criminal Justice: Perspectives Shared by International Experts at the Inter-University Centre of Dubrovnik*. Inter-University Centre of Dubrovnik, 2010; MIERS, D.: "Positivist victimology: A critique", in *International Review of Victimology*, vol. 1(1), 1989, pp. 3-22.; and WILSON, J. K. (Ed.): *The Praeger Handbook of Victimology*, Bloomsbury Publishing, 2019.

¹⁶ SCHÜNEMANN, B.: "Criminal law system and victim dogmatics", in *The science of criminal law at the dawn of the new century: Tribute to Professor José Cerezo*, Madrid: Tecnos, 2002, pp. 159-172.

¹⁷ WALKLATE, S., "Victimology and genocide: Neglected stories?", in *Genocide and Victimology*, London: Routledge, 2020, pp. 23-37.

¹⁸ LEVENE, M., "Why is the twentieth century the century of genocide?", in *Journal of World History*, 2000, pp. 305-336.

¹⁹ ANDERSON, K.: *The Dehumanisation Dynamic: A Criminology of Genocide*, Doctoral Thesis, PhD in Law (Human Rights), Irish Centre for Human Rights, National University of Ireland, 2011.

²⁰ See SCHAFER, S.: "The Beginnings of 'Victimology'", in DRAPKIN, I./Viano, E. (Editors): *Victimology*, Lexington Books, 1974, pp. 17-30; HERRERA, M., *La hora de la víctima: compendio victimológico*, Madrid: Edersa, 1996; FATTAH, E. A., "Victimology: Past, present and future", in *Criminologie*, no. 33(1), 2010, pp. 17-46.

In any case, criminology itself showed and continues to show a general lack of interest in crimes committed by states²¹. In the 20th century, the first genocide was documented²² as that committed by German colonial forces in Namibia, followed by others such as the Armenian genocide, etc., providing an example of the blindness of early criminology and victimology to the crimes that have caused the most victims throughout history: those perpetrated by states themselves²³ and, in general, by political violence and collective²⁴ or mass violence, most of which are now studied as atrocity crimes or international crimes: genocide²⁵, crimes against humanity, war crimes and, more recently, crimes against peace or aggression, to which ecocide could be added²⁶.

IV. Multilevel reasons explaining the oblivion

Reflecting on the ideas of von Mayenburg²⁷ in his 2009 article on the work of Hans von Hentig, with references to Benjamin Mendelsohn, four reasons can be identified to explain why early victimologists did not focus on state or mass violence, but only on interpersonal violence, with a clear victim blaming. These would be as follows:

1) At the beginning of the 20th century, as had happened in criminology at the end of the 19th century, biological, eugenic and evolutionary concepts were transplanted into positivist victimology. In a way, there was a prevailing idea that equality under the law was only really for those considered equal and that social

²¹ COHEN, S.: *States of Denial*, Cambridge: Polity, 2001.

²² Term coined after the Second World War by the jurist Lemkin. See the history of the origin of this term, as opposed to that coined by the jurist Lauterpacht, in SANDS, P.: *East West Street*, New York: Knopf, 2016.

²³ ROTHE, D. L./KAUZLARICH, D., 'A victimology of state crime', in *Towards a Victimology of State Crime*, London: Routledge, 2016, pp. 17-28; SCHABAS, W.A., "Atrocity crimes (genocide, crimes against humanity and war crimes)", in W.A. Schabas, W.A. (Ed.): *The Cambridge Companion to International Criminal Law*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2016, pp. 199-213.

²⁴ VAN DER VELDE, Z.: "The Forgotten People": Victimological Responses to Collective Victimization of Refugees (Doctoral dissertation, Master's Thesis), Tilburg University, 2013.

²⁵ For an understanding of the direct and indirect victimisation of genocide, such as the elimination of entire families, see the fascinating book, with current connotations of the geography of war in Ukraine, by LOWER, W.: *The Ravine: A Family, a Photograph, a Holocaust Massacre Revealed*, Mariner Books, 2021.

²⁶ SCHEFFER, D.: "Genocide and atrocity crimes", in *Genocide Studies and Prevention*, no. 1(3), 2006, pp. 229-250; UNITED NATIONS: *Framework for Analysis of Atrocity Crimes. A Tool for Prevention*, New York: United Nations, 2014.

²⁷ VON MAYENBURG, D.: "Geborene Opfer": Bausteine für eine Geschichte der Viktimologie—Das Beispiel Hans -von Hentig, in *Rechtsgeschichte—Legal History*, 2009, pp. 122–147.

life was seen as a struggle for survival, in a context of belief in the existence of race and its dehumanising hierarchies.

2) The rise of an incipient criminal psychology promoted the idea of personality and the born criminal, along with other classifications, as a being different from any other 'normal' human being. The same happened with victims as those (different) suffering beings. Thus, as indicated above, von Hentig expanded Mendelsohn's typology with categories based on victim vulnerabilities. Something obvious was lost sight of: we can all be victims; there is nothing essential or pathological about being a victim, which does happen, although the possibility of being a victim (or, as it is preferred by many today, a victim-survivor) and being recognised as such is unevenly distributed in society and, specifically, in law.

3) Machismo and sexual violence. The first victimologists were men in an era of institutionalised machismo, including its expressions in science, academia, the courts and professional practice. Women were considered irrational and inferior beings, largely at the service of men. That is why I have suggested that, if the fathers of victimology were von Hentig and Mendelsohn, the mothers were those real women who were blamed for their own suffering or their sexual orientation at those times.

In this regard, as a defence lawyer for men who committed gender-based violence, Mendelsohn was interested in administering a 300-variable questionnaire to the accused, in relation to criminal personality, seeking to question their criminal responsibility and, at the same time, question the credibility of the victim, also in crimes of sexual violence, specifically rape²⁸. On two occasions, in 1934 and 1937, he corresponded with Freud about some cases in which he was involved as a lawyer. In the second of these, Mendelsohn and Freud made clear their assumptions, typical of the time, which have caused so much gratuitous social and institutional damage to marginalised human beings – and continue to do so in many countries, where, for example, homosexuality is still criminalized.

4) Finally, it should be remembered that the professional interests of the first victimologists in building a science at the service of criminal law did not allow them to see other types of harm or the victims themselves.

²⁸ STRINGER, R.: “Mendelsohn’s Victimology before the war”, in *Romanian Journal of Victimology*, 2021, pp. 43–53; and STRINGER, R.: “Rape Myths, Rape Law and Mendelsohn’s Victimology: Law’s ‘Bio-psycho-social’ Witness”, in *Feminist Legal Studies*, no. 33(1), 2025, pp. 47–69.

V. The evolution of an apparent contradiction

Along with the reasons mentioned above, which are more structural, social or cultural in nature, we can point to a fifth cause of the neglect of victimisation by Mendelsohn, a Jewish lawyer who studied at the Faculty of Bucharest between 1930 and 1934, who spoke several languages, tried to practise law and live in Nazi Europe and who, finally, together with his wife and mother, settled in Israel in 1958, where he was unable to work as a lawyer and was employed as a receptionist at the Ministry of Finance.

This cause lies in the impact of individual and collective trauma experiences which, together with the need to survive and forget in post-war society, fuels the silence. This silence was widespread in German society itself, as well as in other countries, until well into the 1960s²⁹. Along with the memory of the Holocaust and other genocides, the emergence of modern victimology plays a fundamental role here. Modern victimology, which no longer blames the victim, seeks to reverse the harms of secondary victimisation and promote the rights of marginalised groups, such as women and children, in recent years from an intersectional perspective³⁰, introducing the issue of victims' needs and interests and their corresponding public obligations into victimology studies in order to move beyond bias and symbolic victim law.

For all these reasons, and although it is a recent discovery in his bibliography, Mendelsohn also evolved with the times and, perhaps, his own personal trajectory had an impact on this. In 1965, he published an article entitled "Are crimes committed under the Nazi regime 'crimes' under common law?", already cited above, in the *Journal of International Law of Diplomatic and Political Sciences*. In it, he refers to dehumanisation, particularly in totalitarian regimes and, specifically, in Nazism. He discusses the cycle of violence and revenge generated by collective or mass victimisation, and criticises the impunity afforded to what he considers to be monstrous crimes which, he argues, are radically different from other crimes and can in no way be justified as mere acts of war, alluding to the pending task of denazification in German law faculties themselves³¹, which leads us to a reflection,

²⁹See MATE, R.: "The victim-violence relationship, a challenge to society", in *Revista de Victimologia/Journal of Victimology*, no. 14, 2022, pp. 9–14. and, in another sense, more narrative and literary, DROSIHN, Y., JANDL, I./KOWOLLIK, E. (Eds.): *Trauma – Generationen – Erzählen. Transgenerationale Narrative in der Gegenwartsliteratur zum ost-, ostmittel- und südosteuropäischen Raum*, Frank & Timme, 2010.

³⁰ DANCIG-ROSENBERG, H./YOSEF, N.: "Crime victimhood and intersectionality", in *Fordham Urban. Law Journal*, vol. 47, 2019, pp. 85-116.

³¹ Cf. RADBRUCH, G.: "Statutory Lawlessness and Supra-Statutory Law", in *Oxford Journal of Legal Studies*, vol. 26(1), 2006, pp. 1–11.

always relevant, on the role of universities as the seedbed and extension of violent and even genocidal ideas .³²

After finding the aforementioned article, through the consultation of the digital archive on Mendelsohn, carried out on 26 May 2025, I found at least fourteen references to the term "genocide", although we still do not know what life was like for Mendelsohn and his family in those dark years.

In any case, Mendelsohn ended up imagining a broader victimology, beyond the concept of crime, at the service of society, a victimology that included victimisation in international crimes. At the same time, he promoted the idea of international conferences in this discipline. In 1991, at one of the symposia of the World Society of Victimology, Mendelsohn received the Hans von Hentig Award, among other honours bestowed upon him by that Society. Today, the World Society of Victimology has a Mendelsohn Award for young academics and, as already mentioned, the victimology group of the European Society of Criminology is promoting the digitisation and study of his archive, in a fitting tribute to the contribution of this author, with all his human contradictions.

VI. Some conclusions

In some writings from the mid-1950s, Mendelsohn criticised criminology for neglecting victims³³ . He wondered why Western societies, which were apparently so humane towards those who broke the law, at least in the written law of democratic countries, were so indifferent to victims, "who, in addition to the suffering inflicted by the aggressor, must bear the burden of proof?". He even alluded to the fact that, despite having obtained the right to compensation in court, "they cannot collect anything because the offender is insolvent?"³⁴. Mendelsohn thus pioneered the recognition of the needs of victims and their exploitation by the criminal justice system, at least for those he considered "less guilty victims". He did so in a contradictory manner, blaming many others, particularly women victims of gender-based violence, and forgetting, somewhat understandably given the context of the time and the impact of the trauma itself, the collective victimisation characteristic of Nazism, war and other dehumanising regimes that shaped the first half of the 20th century. That political violence left its intergenerational legacy of further violence in the decades that followed.

³² On the role of the German university itself in the invention of the concept of race, as well as its tragic and persistent consequences and its rectification, see UNIVERSITY OF JENA: *Jena Declaration*, 2019, <https://www.uni-jena.de/en/22120/jena-declaration>.

³³ With some important but anecdotal exceptions, see, for example, SUTHERLAND, E. H.: *Criminology*, J. B. Lippincott Company, 1924 (see Chapter Three on crime victims and social costs).

³⁴ Op. Cit. MENDELSON, 1956, p. 96.

In any case, there are lessons from Mendelsohn's works and life that should continue to guide us, among which I highlight the following:

1. The constant evolution of victimology towards broader research, based on solid theories, supported by empirical data and ethical principles, in order to reduce the processes of hidden victimisation and, in particular, secondary victimisation in the criminal justice system.

2. The perpetual task of constantly questioning our own myopia and biases, despite, or perhaps precisely because of, our specialisation in the study of victimisation and devictimisation processes, which can only be carried out properly with victims and not on victims, as mere objects of study. So, we can ask ourselves: how are we (victimologists) biased today? Which victims do we fail to see?

3. The growing body of research on the role, impact and responsibility, beyond the criminal, of observers or third parties, in a more complex conception of the couple or the criminal dyad, initially proposed by Mendelsohn³⁵.

4. The unavoidable and disturbing critical question of why it remains so difficult to defend human rights beyond competitive victimhood and without justifying (minimising) other human rights violations or falling into equidistance.

On this last issue, it is more important than ever in our shared global history to uphold the principle of humanity in criminal justice, which is linked to the great legacy of the victims of international crimes: "Never again, against anyone else". Because violence brings more violence, recognising all its forms, with the adequate historical and legal contextualisation³⁶, helps breaking the cycle and monologue of dehumanising victimisation, whether interpersonal, collective or state-sponsored³⁷. In this ethical-legal, criminological and victimological task, we are all involved³⁸, but even more so, the University or academic community.

³⁵ See, initially, in classic criminological studies, LATANÉ, B./DARLEY, J. M.: "Bystander apathy", in *American Scientist*, no. 57(2), 1969, pp. 244-268; and, specifically on the Holocaust, HILBERG, R.: *Perpetrators Victims Bystanders: The Jewish Catastrophe 1933-1945*, HarpersCollins, 1992; as well as EHRENREICH, R. M./COLE, T.: "The perpetrator-bystander-victim constellation: Rethinking genocidal relationships", in *Human Organisation*, no. 64(3), 2005, pp. 213-224; and, in a more complex way, FULBROOK, M.: *Bystander Society: Conformity and Complicity in Nazi Germany and the Holocaust*, Harvard University Press, 2023.

³⁶ Here we can see a contrast of ideas, depending on the community of reference, between ALONSO, R., "Moral Disengagement from Hamas' Atrocities: An Analysis of How the Terrorist Attacks on October 7 have been Justified and Legitimised (Part 1)", in *Studies in Conflict & Terrorism*, 2025, pp. 1-29 and ALONSO, M.: "Victims of Francoism, victims of terrorism. Is it appropriate to label victims?", in X *Victimology Meeting in memory of Professor Antonio Beristain*, 26 November, IVAC/KREI, Donostia/San Sebastián (unpublished paper), 2020. For a current critical reinterpretation, focusing on the war in Gaza, see MOKHIBER, C., "Law on trial: Gaza and the future of the international legal order," in *Dialectical Anthropology*, no. 49(1), 2025, pp. 121-144.

³⁷ BOEHM, O.: "Universalism in Dark Times. And why friendship and enlightenment flourish," in *Public Seminar*, 19 April 2024, together https://publicseminar.org/2024/04/universalism-in-dark-times/?utm_source=substack&utm_medium=email.

³⁸ ROTHBERG, M.: *The Implicated Subject: Beyond Victims and Perpetrators*, Stanford University Press, 2019.

Landmarks about Mendelsohn`s Case studies

Bogdan BUNECI³⁹

Abstract

Benjamin Mendelsohn practiced law in Romania in the first half of the 20th century, and his work profoundly influenced the way victims of crime are perceived and treated. He changed the perspective of an era when the victim was often ignored, demonstrating that victims are an active part in the criminal dynamics and that their personality and behaviour can influence the commission of the crime.

His work in criminal cases promoted a more humane, equitable, and reparation-oriented approach to criminal justice. He demonstrated that victimology has a much larger scope than the criminal sphere, expanding to encompass human vulnerability determined by various physical, mental, psychological, economic, social, or natural factors.

Key-words: legal professions, criminal cases and proceedings, types of victims

1. Benjamin Mendelsohn's personality in the legal profession

Benjamin Mendelsohn practiced law in Romania in the first half of the 20th century, and his work as a lawyer had a profound influence on the way victims of crime are perceived and treated in criminal proceedings.

The victim was often ignored or reduced to a simple evidentiary tool and at that time the focus was placed exclusively on the perpetrator, who after his identification and criminal prosecution was judged and punished. Practicing law in the criminal field, Benjamin Mendelsohn has found through his professional experience that, in reality, victims are an active part in the criminal dynamics and that their personality, behaviour or vulnerability can influence not only the commission of the crime, but also the way it is managed by judicial institutions.

³⁹ Assoc. prof., Law Faculty – Ecological University, Bucharest, President of the Romanian Criminals Lawyers Association, Bucharest, Romania

In his capacity as a defender in criminal cases Benjamin Mendelsohn noticed that in many cases of crimes the victim was not completely uninvolved thus, he published in 1956⁴⁰ a classification that included six types of victims, depending on their degree of responsibility in the commission of the crime, namely:

- the completely innocent victim – has no contribution to the crime, being chosen randomly and did not provoke the perpetrator in any way; for instance, children who have been sexually abused;

- the victim with inadvertent fault – did not want to provoke the act, but through imprudence, negligence or inattention contributed to its occurrence; Example: A car left unlocked in an area known for theft.

- the voluntary victim – consciously accepts to expose oneself to a risk, either for a benefit or for another reason; Example: fraud in contracts.

- the provocative victim – his/her behaviour is provocative and indirectly determines the criminal reaction; Example: the victim provokes an aggressor, to the point that he resorts to violence.

- the aggressor victim – is a victim only formally, because he/she was in fact the initiator of the conflict or criminal act; Example: the victim physically assaults another person and is killed in self-defence.

- imaginary victim – the person claims to be a victim, but in reality, no crime has been committed or he is the perpetrator. Example, when a person for material gain claims that he was raped by the perpetrator.⁴¹

It is important that in those years – 1950 – 1956, as a criminal lawyer, Benjamin Mendelsohn brought up the idea that the victim is not always completely passive or devoid of responsibility, so new research perspectives in criminal law, criminology and forensic psychology were opened.

Also, later he adopted a position substantiating an extensive victimology in the sense that there are victims in several types of events and not only in the criminal sphere due to various factors such as: physical, mental, psychological, economic, political, social or natural.

Benjamin Mendelsohn had a laborious activity in the criminal cases in which he participated as a lawyer, introducing the questionnaire method, where the accused person was to provide details about the needs that led him to commit a crime, such as rape, analysing even the way of carrying out this crime completely, three conditions being necessary, namely:

⁴⁰ B. Mendelsohn, „*A New Branch of Bio-Psychological Science: La Victimology*”, Revue Internationale de Criminologie et de Police Technique, 1956

⁴¹ Ibidem

- a touch as complete as possible on as large an area as possible by interpenetrating the genitals of both sexes;
- a complete touch of the body of the two individuals and especially of the parts closest to the genitals;
- a position that is as comfortable as possible to be as less tiring as possible, thus increasing the intensity and duration of the act.

Thus, he mentions a woman's clothing as an obstacle to mating, and when the victim resists, the perpetrator is obliged to use at least one hand to undress her.

2. Criminological approach

From a criminological point of view, in rape, the author shows that it was necessary to turn the victim from an upright position to a horizontal position, to hold the victim by force (she can defend herself with her fists, scratch the attacker, bite him on the face or chin). The perpetrator fights for the immobilization of the upper part of the victim, after which follows the phase of immobilizing the victim in the lower part to be subjected to rape. He mentions here that the vigorous state of the aggressor, which is not to be judged by that of the individual in a normal state, but by that which he possesses when he is under the influence of the primary instincts, in this state his physical strength is the result of the combination of the two primitive instincts, the sexual instinct and the aggressive instinct.

Even if the victim had reacted with violence, the perpetrator was inclined to tolerate violence, and in other cases the victim even became violent.

3. Mendelsohn's Case studies

In his studies, also on the crime of rape, Benjamin Mendelsohn⁴² shows that the magistrate must not forget the fundamental principles of judicial law in criminal proceedings, namely: 1. Innocence is presumed – guilt must be proven. The accusation is always a hypothesis to be verified – never a theorem to be proved; 2. The clue is never absolute proof – it can provide a very high probability, but not certainty.

As evidence, he brings into question in the case of the crime of rape the forensic examination of both the victim (showing that the recent perforation of

⁴² B. Mendelsohn, *Le viol en Criminologie*, Giustizia penale, parte I- I presupposti del diritto e della procedura penale, Societa Anonima tip "Leonardo da Vinci", 1940

the hymen and the presence of spermatozoa may constitute an indication – and not a proof in the strict sense, since it only indicates that the sexual act or rape took place, but does not allow the identification of the active agent) and of the defendant – regarding the physical examination of him for any traces caused by the victim.

Another means of proof concerning somatic examinations and blood tests of the accused when the victim has contracted a venereal disease, thereby demonstrating that the infected area in the case of the genitals, may lead to a stronger assumption that the accused person could be the perpetrator of the crime, as well as whether the parents or persons living with the victim have previously suffered from the same disease.

With regard to the hearing of witnesses in the criminal cases in which Benjamin Mendelsohn participated as a lawyer, he pointed out in particular that for minors these hearings must be carried out by experienced persons because the child's imagination constitutes a system of thought specific to him and different from that of the adult. He showed that a child is not able to tell the truth until after the "age of reason" (after about 8 years old of age). That is why he proposed that the child's interrogation be carried out by a specialist in psychology applied to minors.

He pleaded for the reform in the judiciary regarding the occupation of these positions by women. He mentioned that the psychology of young girls in sexual problems and especially of young children is an obstacle in obtaining an unreserved account of the stages of committing the crime of sexual assault that involves their greatest bodily and moral intimacy. Thus, he proposed some reforms, namely:

a) at least the first hearing, in particular in cases of sexual assault, must be conducted compulsorily through a psychology expert;

b) the prohibition of persons directly interested in the trial or whose interests do not require their presence, or whose presence, in the opinion of the expert, could influence the child's statements;

c) the appearance of a family reunion. This is the most important and innovative one that Benjamin Mendelsohn suggested. He considered it necessary to set up a special room for the trial of these crimes, when the real or alleged victims are minors, as well as adequate furniture that would resemble as much as possible the living room of a residential house.

d) The questions that were asked by the president of the panel of judges had to be asked through the expert so that he could address them to the child.

Even if the approach to rape reflects the limits of the era in which Benjamin Mendelsohn lived, the approach to the victims of a crime is still a problem today when the victim must be recognized not only for the material or physical damage suffered but also for the profound and lasting psychological effects.

If victimization represents a rupture of the personal safety system that can generate post-traumatic stress (nightmares, hypervigilance and avoidance of certain places or people), generalized anxiety (the person can live with a state of tension, state or uncertainty affecting the ability to socialize and work), depression (if they do not receive psychological support they can have a state of helplessness, guilt and isolation), decreased self-esteem (domestic violence, sexual abuse, where the victim comes to internalize shame and guilt), this victimization can also have social consequences, distrust in institutions and most of all it is essential to provide specialized support as a result of trauma, anxiety and marginalization.

4. Reflection of Mendelsohn's vision in modern legislation

Benjamin Mendelsohn's activity as a criminal lawyer not only had a founding impact on the development of victimology as a science, where through theoretical reflections and commitment to **victims' rights** he contributed decisively to the recognition of the victim as a procedural subject and not only, but also in the current criminal procedural regulations the victims benefit from the right to defense, as main procedural subjects provided for by Article 10 of the Code of Criminal Procedure⁴³, as well as to respect for human dignity and private life provided for by Article 11 of the Code of Criminal Procedure⁴⁴. They may exercise civil action in criminal proceedings, being considered as main procedural subjects provided for in Article 33 of the Code of Criminal Procedure, having the rights provided for in the provisions of Article 81 of the Code of Criminal Procedure.

With regard to victims, the provisions of Article 111 of the Code of Criminal Procedure⁴⁵ are essential, especially paragraphs 6 – 10, namely:

(6) In the case of injured persons for whom the existence of specific protection needs has been established under the law, the judicial body shall order

⁴³ <http://legislatie.just.ro/Public/DetaliuDocument/120611>

⁴⁴ <http://legislatie.just.ro/Public/DetaliuDocument/120611>

⁴⁵ Idem

one or more of the following measures, without prejudice to the proper conduct of the trial or to the rights and interests of the parties:

- a) hearing them in premises designed or adapted for this purpose;
- b) hearing them through or in the presence of a psychologist or other specialist in counselling victims;
- c) their hearing, as well as their eventual re-hearing, shall be carried out by the same person, if this is possible and if the judicial body considers that this does not prejudice the proper conduct of the trial or the rights and interests of the parties;
- d) hearing them by videoconference or other technical means of communication at the place where they benefit from the temporary accommodation protection measure.

(7) The hearing and, as the case may be, the re-hearing by the criminal investigation bodies of the injured persons who were victims of the crimes provided for in art. 197, 199, 209-2161, 218, 2181, 219, 2191, 221, 222, 223 and 374 of the Criminal Code⁴⁶, as well as in other cases where, due to the circumstances of the commission of the act, this is considered necessary shall be carried out only by a person of the same sex as the injured person. If this is not possible, without prejudice to the proper conduct of the trial or to the rights and interests of the parties, the hearing of these injured persons and, where appropriate, their re-hearing may be carried out by a person who is not of the same sex as the injured person, with the consent of the lawyer and a psychologist or other specialist in counselling victims.

(8) If the injured person is a minor, the recording of his/her hearing by audio-video technical means is mandatory in all cases. When video recording is not possible, the recording shall in all cases be carried out by audio technical means.

(8¹) The hearing of the injured person up to 14 years of age shall take place in the presence of one of the parents, guardian or persons or representative of the institution to which the minor is entrusted for upbringing and education, as well as in the presence of a psychologist, established by the judicial body. The psychologist will provide specialized counselling to the minor throughout the judicial proceedings.

(9) The hearing of the injured person by the judicial body that has registered a complaint regarding the commission of a crime shall take place immediately, and, if this is not possible, it shall be carried out after the filing of the complaint, without undue delay.

⁴⁶ <https://legislatie.just.ro/Public/DetaliiDocumentAfis/268760>

(10) The statement given by the injured person under the conditions of para. (9) shall constitute evidence even if it was administered before the commencement of the criminal investigation.

In the sense of the defense of minors, by Law no. 35/1997⁴⁷ on the organization and functioning of the Ombudsman institution (republished in the Official Gazette, Part I no. 181 of February 27, 2018) the Children's Advocate institution was introduced, which defends the rights of children up to 18 years of age, supports and encourages the respect and promotion of their rights. The Children's Advocate intervenes in situations regarding physical, mental, sexual abuse, disappearances of children, the phenomenon of bullying, poverty, the situation in placement centers, relationships within schools and kindergartens, the integration of children with disabilities, the preservation of personal ties between children and the people to whom they are attached, the situation of children whose parents have gone to work abroad, as well as in any situation in which children's rights are not respected.

Conclusion

It is said that a man who works is always interesting and noble, because where he carries out his activity, he leaves something from the heart and in a way gets closer to nature, to the truth. Through his work in criminal cases, Benjamin Mendelsohn has made his ideas based on victim protection policies and the evolution of criminal justice towards a more humane, equitable and reparation-oriented approach.

Furthermore, the article illustrates how his vision has been assimilated by contemporary Romanian legal doctrine. Today, Mendelsohn's ideas are directly reflected in the current Romanian Criminal Procedure Code—which establishes the victim as a main procedural subject—and in modern protective institutions, such as the Children's Advocate and specialized hearing procedures for minors.

He showed in his works that it is necessary to take into account the vulnerability of humans in general, so that victimology has a much larger scope than the victim-offender relationship, going beyond the area of criminological concerns.

⁴⁷ <https://avp.ro/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/lege35.pdf>